

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On the meridional asymmetry of the poleward-displaced intertropical convergence zone

Divya Sri Praturi^{ORCID} | Bjorn Stevens^{ORCID}Climate Physics, Max Planck Institute for
Meteorology, Hamburg, Germany**Correspondence**Divya Sri Praturi, Max Planck Institute for
Meteorology, Hamburg, Germany.Email: divya-sri.praturi@mpimet.mpg.de**Funding information**EC Horizon2020 project NextGEMS,
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Forschung (BMBF) project WarmWorld,
Grant/Award Number: 01LK2202B**Abstract**

We analyze the mean dynamical structure of the lower atmosphere over the tropical East Pacific and Atlantic basins during boreal summer, when the sea-surface temperature (SST) is maximized well poleward of the Equator. We use the data from a global, coupled storm-resolving simulation performed using the ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic (ICON) model with an explicit representation of convection (ICON Sapphire) for our analysis. It has previously been hypothesized that inertial instability plays a role in determining the latitude of the intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ). Seasonal mean composites of absolute vertical vorticity and convergence about the latitude of maximum precipitable water suggest that convergence emerges well within the region of inertial stability. We show that the dynamical structure can be explained better using the mean momentum balance. Equatorial pressure gradients near the surface must be balanced by advection, leading to the acceleration of southerlies and advection of negative absolute vertical vorticity north of the Equator. The strengthening westerlies, due to negative relative vorticity in the southerly flow, balance the pressure gradients south of the ITCZ, leading to deceleration of southerlies and dynamic convergence. The dynamical nature of convergence in the southerlies is fundamentally different from the convergence observed in the northerlies, where the pressure gradients can be balanced by easterlies owing to their more poleward location. The resulting dynamical structure is asymmetrical, with a concentration of convergence in the southerly trade-wind regime. We also observe that the relative vorticity in the ITCZ depends on the ITCZ latitude, and increases as the ITCZ moves to the north.

KEYWORDS

dynamic convergence, global storm-resolving simulations, inertial instability, ITCZ

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1 | INTRODUCTION

The intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ) is the region of trade-wind convergence and ensuing upward motion in an unstable tropical atmosphere, leading to high cloudiness and precipitation. It is typically located above warmer sea-surface temperatures (SST). During boreal summer, when the SST is maximized well poleward of the Equator, the observed structure of the atmosphere near the surface is complex and asymmetric about the latitude of confluence, where the northerly and southerly trade winds meet (Hastenrath & Lamb, 1977, 1978, 2004; Windmiller & Stevens, 2024). A few aspects of the asymmetrical dynamical structure observed in the eastern parts of the Pacific and Atlantic basins are summarized below. (i) The southeasterly trades turn southwesterly at about 5°N, as they move towards the ITCZ. (ii) The recurvature latitude (5°N) separates regions of divergence (seen to its south) and convergence (seen to its north). (iii) The latitudes of maximum convergence and precipitation are located about 350 km south of the confluence. Using recent ship-based measurements, Windmiller and Stevens (2024) note that the ITCZ during boreal summer is characterized by a broad meridional region of convergence, often with convection intensifying at the edges. The precipitation at the southern edge of the ITCZ is also greater than that seen at the northern edge.

Tomas and Webster (1997) hypothesize that, given sufficiently warm SSTs and an unstable atmosphere, inertial instability plays a role in determining the latitude of the off-Equator ITCZ, which is typically seen during boreal summer in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins, as the cross-equatorial pressure gradients are large enough to advect negative absolute vertical vorticity into the Northern Hemisphere. Making use of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Tropical Ocean Global Atmosphere–World Climate Research Program (TOGA-WCRP) dataset at T42 resolution (2.8°), Tomas and Webster (1997) show that the latitude of neutral inertial instability, where absolute vertical vorticity is zero, separates the regions of divergence and convergence, and provide arguments to establish inertial instability as the cause for off-Equator convection. In zonally symmetric balance models with heating off-Equator where an asymmetrical Hadley circulation with a stronger cross-equatorial cell is seen to develop (Lindzen & Hou, 1988), inertial instability at the latitudes of the cross-equatorial Hadley cell has also been examined as a potential explanation for its greater strength (Hack *et al.*, 1989).

With this context, we are interested in answering the following questions regarding the structure of the lower

atmosphere in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins during boreal summer.

1. Why is the region of surface convergence broad and asymmetrical about the latitude of confluence? To what extent is the mean surface structure consistent with the hypothesis of Tomas and Webster (1997)?
2. How does the structure change aloft, above the boundary layer?

To answer these questions, we make use of a global coupled storm-resolving model, as such models connect convection to the flow more directly (Satoh *et al.*, 2019). If the ITCZ is driven partly by a dynamic instability, such as the one suggested by Tomas and Webster (1997), we need a model that allows the convection to respond naturally to the dynamics. Convective parameterizations prevent such a natural relationship between convection and dynamics, and work more indirectly through large-scale thermodynamics. This has been shown to be important over land, where an explicit representation of convection leads to a very different coupling to the surface than does a thermodynamic coupling using statistical representations of convection (Hohenegger *et al.*, 2009). Global storm-resolving models are also shown to have a better representation of the diurnal cycle of precipitation (Song *et al.*, 2024). In idealized settings, cloud-resolving simulations with explicit convection have long been used to understand the questions related to convective organization (Muller, 2013; Muller & Bony, 2015; Wing, 2019). Ensuring consistency with the underlying SSTs requires a coupled approach, which is difficult to impose in idealized models. Furthermore, an equatorial cold tongue has been shown to play a key role in the observed Northern Hemisphere preference for the ITCZ in the eastern ocean basins, emphasizing further the need for a coupled approach (Wang & Wang, 1999). We make use of first simulations that are global km-scale, coupled with explicit representation of convection, which provides a new type of laboratory to investigate the above questions related to ITCZ dynamics. While many previous studies have used energetic frameworks (Adam *et al.*, 2016a, 2016b; Bischoff & Schneider, 2014) to understand precipitation, we examine the asymmetry in force balances to understand the winds.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a description of the simulation data, our compositing technique, and the notation followed in this article. The near-surface structure of the atmosphere is examined in Section 3, and the vertical structure is presented in Section 4. A conceptual picture of the observed asymmetrical structure and its dependence on the latitude of

maximum SST are discussed in Section 5. We provide a summary of our findings in Section 6.

2 | DATA AND METHODS

We analyze the data from a global coupled storm-resolving simulation, *ngc3028*, performed using the ICOSahe-dral Nonhydrostatic model in the Sapphire configuration (ICON Sapphire: Segura *et al.*, 2022; Hohenegger *et al.*, 2023). *ngc3028* employs a horizontal grid spacing of 5 km and the atmosphere is discretized into 90 vertical levels. The ocean adopts the same horizontal discretization as the atmosphere and consists of 128 levels in the vertical direction. The simulation is initialized on January 20, 2020 using the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) and proceeds until August 31, 2025. The output of *ngc3028* is available at different spatial resolutions interpolated on to a Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelization (HEALPix) grid (Gorski *et al.*, 2005).

In this study, we analyze instantaneous field output on a HEALPix grid with a horizontal resolution of 0.18° , sampled at three-hourly intervals during boreal summer (a total of five years from 2020 to 2024). The longitudinal domains of the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ considered in this study are $[125^\circ\text{W}, 105^\circ\text{W}]$ and $[40^\circ\text{W}, 20^\circ\text{W}]$, respectively (see Figure S1 of the Supplementary Material for the regions of the East Pacific and Atlantic basins considered in this study).

2.1 | ITCZ identification

While many definitions, based on moist static energy (Kang *et al.*, 2008) and mass streamfunction (Ceppi *et al.*, 2013), have been used to identify the zonal mean latitude of the ITCZ, in this study we are interested in a local definition in order to be able to composite across the longitudinal variations in ITCZ latitude. As the HEALPix grid is not an equal-longitude grid, to enable a local definition for the ITCZ we bin the data by longitude using a binning of 0.25° . The diagnosed position of the ITCZ is not sensitive to a factor of two change in bin size (Figure S2 of the Supplementary Material). We utilize an index set to the latitude of maximum precipitable water (PW) in $[0^\circ, 20^\circ\text{N}]$ in any longitude bin to identify the ITCZ locally. The precipitable water field is filtered to remove values that are smaller than the 90th percentile value of their tropical ocean monthly means (latitudes between 20°S and 20°N) before the latitude of the maximum is determined. Filtering helps ensure that the maximum PW is identified in the tropical latitudes where the ITCZ is expected to be present. The seasonal march of ITCZ determined using precipitable water also

FIGURE 1 Seasonal march of the five-year zonal mean of the ITCZ latitude ($\lambda_{\text{PW}, \text{max}}$) in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.com)]

agreed reasonably well with that determined using precipitation (Figure S4 in the Supplementary Material) following Hohenegger and Stevens (2022). The precipitation-based index was noisier in the East Pacific basin (during periods of edge intensification or lull in precipitation in that longitude). For this reason, we adopted the maximum in precipitable water.

We plot the five-year mean seasonal march of the zonal mean ITCZ latitude in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins during boreal summer in Figure 1. The zonal mean ITCZ latitude in the East Pacific in *ngc3028* is located at approximately 8°N in June and migrates north to 12°N in August. The Atlantic ITCZ is located at 4°N in June and migrates to about 10°N by August. The seasonal, zonal mean positions of the ITCZ in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins are 10.8°N and 8.1°N , respectively, as indicated on the y-axis of Figure 1. The meridional migration of the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ, obtained using daily precipitable water fields, agrees well with the ECMWF Reanalysis dataset, ERA5 (Hersbach *et al.*, 2020 and Figure S3 of the Supplementary Material).

2.2 | Compositing technique

We obtain the boreal summer statistics for the ITCZ using the following compositing technique. (i) In each of the longitudinal bins, after the ITCZ latitude (PW maximum) is determined using the method described in Section 2.1, we perform a local coordinate transformation, such that the origin of the local coordinate system along the meridional direction is translated to the ITCZ latitude (PW maximum), that is,

$$\lambda' = \lambda - \lambda_{\text{PW}, \text{max}}. \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, λ represents the original latitudes, which are then translated with respect to the latitude of the maximum PW, $\lambda_{PW, \max}$, to obtain the latitude of the composites, λ' . If the ITCZ does not exist at a particular longitudinal bin, then the latitudes in the bin are translated based on the zonal mean PW maximum latitude (denoted by square brackets):

$$\lambda' = \lambda - [\lambda_{PW, \max}]. \quad (2)$$

(ii) We evaluate the local zonal means in each of the longitudinal bins. (iii) The zonal mean of the basin is then computed by taking the mean of the local zonal means in the translated ITCZ-based coordinate system, λ' , and as a result we account for the variability in the ITCZ latitudes (Figure S6 of the Supplementary Material) across different longitudes in the basin. (iv) Finally, we compute the temporal mean (five-year average of the basin zonal means during boreal summer), which provides us with a composited view of the statistics with respect to the ITCZ. The composites of the small-scale variables of vorticity and convergence are insensitive to the index used in the ITCZ identification (Figure S5 of the Supporting Information).

2.3 | Theory and notation

2.3.1 | Winds

The governing equations for zonally averaged zonal and meridional wind speeds, upon neglecting the contribution of the terms containing vertical velocities and horizontal eddy fluxes, are given by

$$V \frac{dU}{dy} \approx fV - \frac{\tau_x(0)}{h}, \quad (3)$$

$$V \frac{dV}{dy} \approx -fU - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dP}{dy} - \frac{\tau_y(0)}{h}. \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, U , V , and P are the zonally averaged zonal and meridional wind speeds and pressure, y is the meridional coordinate, f denotes the Coriolis parameter, $\tau_x(0)$, $\tau_y(0)$ denote the surface drag acting along the zonal and meridional directions, and h is the boundary-layer height. Ekman balance along the meridional direction, starting from Equation (4), would imply that

$$fU = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dP}{dy} - \frac{\tau_y(0)}{h}. \quad (5)$$

When the SST is maximized poleward of the Equator, the pressure minimum also moves poleward (Lindzen & Nigam, 1987; Tomas & Webster, 1997), leading to

negative pressure gradients in near-equatorial latitudes close to the surface. As $f \rightarrow 0$ in near-equatorial latitudes, Ekman balance (Equation 5) would mean that the pressure gradients are balanced solely by surface drag. However, observations show substantial acceleration of southerlies north of the Equator (Hastenrath, 2012). This hints towards the role played by the meridional advection term, VdV/dy , in near-equatorial latitudes. This is evident in Figure 2—depicting the terms in Equation (4) for months June, July, and August (JJA) in the year 2020—where pressure gradients near the Equator are largely balanced by advection. Advection is non-negligible in the meridional momentum budget (Equation 4), from near-equatorial latitudes to the ITCZ, thereby violating Ekman balance (Equation 5), as also shown by Gonzalez and Schubert (2019) using a dry slab boundary-layer model for the East Pacific. In Gonzalez and Schubert (2019), a stronger violation of Ekman balance is seen with increasing resolution as the magnitude of advection increases. As a result, Gonzalez and Schubert (2019) emphasize the need for high-resolution simulations for studying boundary-layer processes in the ITCZ. Asymmetry about the ITCZ is also evident in the Coriolis term in Figure 2. However, in the northerlies, which occupy more poleward positions (greater f) compared with the southerlies, the Ekman balance given in Equation (5) can be more easily upheld, leading to the frictional deceleration and convergence of the northerlies. Observational composites of Janota (1972) also show that the winds to the north of the ITCZ veer as suggested by the Northern Hemisphere Ekman layer, whereas those to the south (around 1° – 4° N) do not veer—suggesting a possible advection of the Southern Hemisphere Ekman layer underlying this asymmetry.

2.3.2 | Vorticity and convergence

The zonally averaged relative vertical vorticity, ζ , can be expressed as

$$\zeta \equiv -\frac{dU}{dy}, \quad (6)$$

as the zonal average of terms containing zonal derivatives is zero. The governing equation for ζ can be obtained by simply differentiating the mean zonal wind Equation (3) with respect to the y -coordinate (and neglecting the friction term):

$$V \frac{d\zeta}{dy} \approx -V\beta + \eta C, \quad \eta \equiv \zeta + f, \quad C \equiv -\frac{dV}{dy}. \quad (7)$$

Here η and C denote the zonal means of absolute vertical vorticity and convergence, respectively. In the above Equation (7) for ζ , we do not discuss the role played by

FIGURE 2 Zonal averages of various terms in the meridional momentum equation (Equation 4) at 311 m during JJA for the year 2020. Pressure gradients computed using spherical harmonics are smoothed using cubic spline interpolation to remove fine-scale oscillations. The surface momentum flux applied to the entire boundary-layer depth is one of the output fields in ngc3028. A range for $\tau_y(0)/h$ (shaded region) in Equation (4) is computed by taking h to range from 300 to 1000 m. The abscissa labels, $\lambda = 11.7$ (a) and $\lambda = 9.0$ (b), denote the latitudes of the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ during JJA 2020. The error bars indicate the maximum and minimum JJA-mean ITCZ latitudes over the five-year simulation period. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

surface friction explicitly to simply highlight the behavior of $-V\beta$ and ηC . Surface friction, however, plays an important role in the boundary layer in damping ζ (Tomas *et al.*, 1999; Tomas & Webster, 1997). The equation for absolute vertical vorticity, η , can be obtained by adding a $Df/Dt = V\beta$ term to both left- and right-hand sides of the above vorticity equation (Equation 7):

$$V \frac{d\eta}{dy} \approx \eta C. \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) suggests that, in regions of negligible convergence, that is, $C \approx 0$,

$$\frac{d\zeta}{dy} \approx -\beta, \quad (9)$$

and the meridional gradient of relative vorticity is negative, as β is non-negative for all latitudes. The above result can also be inferred from an absolute vorticity conservation standpoint: that is, when $C \approx 0$ in Equation (8), the meridional gradient of absolute vorticity is zero, $d\eta/dy \approx 0$. As f is an increasing function of y , ζ decreases with y when $d\eta/dy \approx 0$. Or, simply, conservation of absolute vorticity (or $\eta \equiv \zeta + f = \text{constant}$) would imply that the relative vorticity (ζ) of the southerly air parcels would decrease as they move to the north (increasing f). In the case of northerly air parcels, this would imply increasing ζ as the parcels move to the south. In both cases, this results in negative $d\zeta/dy$, as shown by Equation (9).

In regions of strong convergence, such as those seen in the ITCZ, both ζ and η would be amplified by the process of

vortex-stretching convergence, given by ηC . The strength of the vortex-stretching process depends on the magnitudes of absolute vorticity, η , and convergence, C . Through η ($\equiv \zeta + f$), we can expect the magnitudes of vertical vorticities in the ITCZ to exhibit a positive correlation with the latitude at which the ITCZ is situated.

Analogous to the vorticity Equation (7), we can derive the equation for C by computing the meridional gradient of the V Equation (4):

$$V \frac{dC}{dy} \approx \frac{d}{dy}(Uf) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d^2 P}{dy^2} \approx U\beta - f\zeta + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d^2 P}{dy^2}. \quad (10)$$

Based on the above equation, when zonal winds are westerly, ζ is anti-cyclonic and $d^2 P/dy^2$ is positive (in the vicinity of a pressure minimum), convergence will (i) increase with y in the southerly regime and (ii) decrease with y in the northerly regime. Alternatively, in the southerlies, divergence can increase with y ($Vd(-C)/dy > 0$), if $d(-Uf)/dy > 0$ or $-d^2 P/dy^2 > 0$. The latter is expected in eastern ocean basins, where upwelling results in an SST minimum near the Equator, leading to a pressure maximum (Lindzen & Nigam, 1987).

3 | MEAN SURFACE STRUCTURE

The composites of sea-surface temperature in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins (Figure 3a) exhibit a minimum a few degrees south of the Equator. North of the Equator, the SSTs rise and maximum SST is located (i) to the north of the East Pacific ITCZ and (ii) just south of the Atlantic

FIGURE 3 Composites of (a) sea-surface temperature, (b) surface pressure, (c) zonal wind speed, and (d) meridional wind speed with respect to the ITCZ (maximum PW) in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins. The shading in each of the plots denotes the interannual standard deviation in the composited statistics. Gray vertical dashes in (c) and (d) denote the latitudes where westerly wind is onset in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins. The abscissa labels, $\lambda' = -10.8$ and $\lambda' = -8.1$, denote the location of the Equator relative to the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ, respectively. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

ITCZ. On the other hand, surface pressure (Figure 3b) has a minimum at the ITCZ in both East Pacific and Atlantic basins. The gradient of pressure is negative to the south of the ITCZ and positive to the north of the ITCZ. The magnitude of negative pressure gradient at the Equator is not too high; however, the negative pressure gradients steepen and become more negative as we move north of the Equator towards the ITCZ. In latitudes much south of the Equator, the negative gradient of pressure is balanced by the presence of easterlies (Figure 3c). As discussed in Section 2.3.1, geostrophic balance cannot be achieved in near-Equator latitudes. In the latitudes north of the Equator, such a balance would require westerlies, and westerlies are seen only in latitudes that are close to the ITCZ (Figure 3c). As a result, in latitudes that are close to the Equator (negligible Uf) and to the north of it where easterly winds are seen, mean momentum balance can be achieved when the advection term, VdV/dy , is positive. For the southerly wind regime ($V > 0$), $VdV/dy > 0$ indicates near-surface divergence and acceleration ($dV/dy > 0$), as seen from the meridional wind-speed composites in Figure 3d. The gray vertical dashes in the composites of zonal wind (Figure 3c) and meridional wind (Figure 3d) show that the latitudes of onset of westerly winds roughly correspond to the maxima in meridional wind speed. These latitudes are approximately 4.0° and 2.5° south of the East

Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ. The above mean momentum balance offers a potential explanation as to why a strong divergence is seen in the observations of Hastenrath and Lamb (2004) to the north of the Equator during boreal summer—when the SST maximum is more poleward of the SST minimum—and not in austral summer, when the SST minimum south of the Equator is not very pronounced. As the southerlies move further north towards the ITCZ, the strengthening westerlies, together with surface friction, balance the pressure gradients and advection, and lead to the deceleration of southerlies and dynamic convergence. The latitude of confluence, where $V = 0$ in Figure 3d, is located 1° and 0.56° north of the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ. In the region of northerlies, as we move towards the ITCZ, the positive pressure gradients weaken and can be balanced by easterlies (Coriolis) and friction, owing to their more poleward location.

The composites of absolute vertical vorticity (Figure 4a) at a geopotential height of 311 m indicate that the inertial instability criteria based on the parcel method are met (Tomas *et al.*, 1999; Tomas & Webster, 1997), that is, regions where $\eta < 0$ north of the Equator. The latitudes of neutral inertial stability or $\eta = 0$ are approximately 8° and 4° south of the ITCZ in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins, respectively. The composites of convergence at 311 m in Figure 4b also show that $\eta = 0$ is not

FIGURE 4 Composites of (a) absolute vertical vorticity, (b) convergence, and (c) relative vertical vorticity at 311 m with respect to the ITCZ (maximum PW) in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins. Gray vertical dashes denote the latitude of (a) neutral inertial stability and (b) onset of convergence. See Figure 3 for details regarding the shading and abscissa labels. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

collocated with $C = 0$, which is located about 2.6° south of the ITCZ in both the basins. The latitudes of neutral inertial stability are also located equatorward of the latitudes of maximum meridional wind speed (Figure 3d) in both the basins. Hovmöller diagrams of the zonal mean convergence in Figure 5 also show that convergence is onset in the southerlies close to the westerly wind regime ($U = 0$), poleward even of the latitude of neutral inertial instability ($\eta = 0$). Therefore, the hypotheses of Tomas and Webster (1997) that inertial instability plays a role in determining the location of near-Equator convection and convergence exists poleward of $\eta = 0$ do not hold true for height levels close to the surface. The onset of convergence in the southerly regime is dynamically driven. This appears to reflect the mean-meridional momentum balance (Figure 2), as the latitude where winds turn westerly is a better indicator of convergence. Maximum convergence (Figure 4b) is seen at the ITCZ, where the winds are southerly. The region of convergence spans a broader range of latitudes to the north of the ITCZ, as a result of Ekman balance (Figure 2). The composites for η (Figure 4a) and ζ (Figure 4c) agree reasonably well with the conceptual picture obtained using Equation (7). While the conservation of absolute vorticity does not really hold true (non-trivial values for C in Figure 4b), the slope of η , $d\eta/dy$, is considerably reduced between the Equator and the latitude of neutral inertial stability, $\eta = 0$. This reduction in slope is a consequence of the strengthening

of the clockwise turning tendency (Figure 4c)—seen from the relative vertical vorticity composites where $\zeta < 0$ and $d\zeta/dy < 0$ —in the southerlies as they move north towards the ITCZ. A minimum in ζ is seen to the north of the neutral inertial stability latitude, $\eta = 0$, and close to the latitudes of maximum meridional wind speed. In these latitudes, where, $\eta > 0$ and $C < 0$ (seen between the solid and the dashed lines in Figure 5), both β and ηC contribute to a stronger negative slope of ζ . Westerly winds that result from recurving of the winds due to strong clockwise tendencies are seen close to minimum ζ (Figures 3c and 4c). As the convergence increases, ζ increases and a maximum is achieved in the ITCZ where convergence is also a maximum. The maximum value of ζ in the East Pacific ITCZ is greater than that of the Atlantic ITCZ, hinting that the latitude of the ITCZ plays a role in determining the magnitude of vorticity. Counterclockwise tendencies increase in the northerlies as they move south towards the ITCZ, as the slope of relative vorticity is negative, that is, $d\zeta/dy < 0$.

4 | A COMPOSITE VIEW OF THE VERTICAL STRUCTURE

At 1515 m, south of the Equator in both East Pacific and Atlantic basins, strongly negative pressure gradients (Figure 6c) are seen that drive a deeper layer of

FIGURE 5 Hovmöller plots of zonal mean convergence at 311 m in (a) East Pacific and (b) Atlantic basins during JJA 2020. A running time average of 24 h is applied on all the fields plotted. The latitudinal positions of $\eta = 0$ (solid) and $U = 0$ (dashed) are overlaid. The abscissa labels, $\lambda = 11.7$ and $\lambda = 9.0$, denote the location of the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ in JJA 2020. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

cross-equatorial southerly flow. At 4108 m, these pressure gradients south of the Equator are considerably reduced (Figure 6a). Between the Equator and the ITCZ, at both 1515 and 4108 m, the pressure gradients are near-negligible or even positive (East Pacific), unlike the surface (Figure 3b), where $dP/dy < 0$. As a result, aloft at these latitudes, the strong negative pressure gradients that favor the acceleration of southerlies are absent. A pressure minimum can still be found at the ITCZ, an indication that warming in the vicinity of convection can be felt even at higher levels, especially in the East Pacific. The meridional pressure gradients to the north of the ITCZ have remained similar or increased in magnitude at higher levels, reflecting the greater ability of Coriolis to balance pressure gradients and revealing the possible limitation of the weak temperature gradient approximation for latitudes poleward of 10° .

Due to the weakening of surface friction effects aloft, stronger easterlies are needed to balance the pressure gradients south of the Equator at 1515 m (Figure 6d) than at the surface (Figure 3c). At 4108 m, as the pressure gradients take near-zero values to the south of the ITCZ, the easterlies (Figure 6b) are much weaker than at the surface and 1515 m (Figure 6d). On the other hand, to the north of the ITCZ, due to stronger pressure gradients aloft (especially at 4108 m), the strength of easterlies is higher compared with the surface. In addition, in the latitudes north of the ITCZ, stronger easterlies in the Atlantic (African easterly jet) compared with the East Pacific are

indicative of the presence of stronger pressure gradients (Figure 6a). At 1515 m, the development of westerlies is seen close to the ITCZ, even though the pressure gradients are not strongly negative north of the Equator.

The meridional winds at 1515 m in Figure 7c, south of the Equator, are divergent. Divergence and cross-equatorial winds are stronger in the Atlantic, as the negative pressure gradients (Figure 6c) are stronger and easterlies (Figure 6d) are weaker, compared with the East Pacific basin. Between the Equator and the ITCZ, the winds are mostly convergent in nature, except at a few latitudes close to the ITCZ where divergent tendencies are seen. The mean momentum balance considered in Equation (4) does not hold true, as meridional wind convergence in a region of zero pressure gradients cannot be balanced by easterly winds. One can expect vertical transport to play a key role, as convergence at this height level (1515 m) coupled with divergence at the surface is indicative of a shallow circulation south of the ITCZ. The meridional winds at 4108 m (Figure 7a) are the weakest of all the three height levels considered. North of the ITCZ, a deeper circulation is expected than to its south, as divergence in meridional wind is first evident at 4108 m (Figure 7a) in these latitudes.

At 1515 m (Figure 7d), the region of inertial instability in the East Pacific is extended more poleward compared with the surface, whereas this region moves slightly equatorward in the Atlantic basin. The value of η in the East Pacific ITCZ is higher than that of the Atlantic ITCZ. At

FIGURE 6 Composites of pressure (left) and zonal wind (right) at 1515 m (bottom) and 4108 m (top). See Figure 3 for details regarding the shading and abscissa labels. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 7 Composites of meridional wind speed (left) and absolute vertical vorticity (right) at 1515 m (bottom) and 4108 m (top). The vertical gray dashes in (d) denote the latitude of neutral inertial instability at 1515 m. See Figure 3 for details regarding the shading and abscissa labels. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

4108 m (Figure 7b), η remains close to f , except for latitudes close to the ITCZ and those 5° north of the Atlantic ITCZ. Inertial instability is also absent in both the basins at this height level. The difference between vorticities in the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ is considerably reduced at 4108 m compared with lower height levels, 1515 and 311 m. The magnitudes of convergence in the ITCZ at

1515 (Figure 8c) and 4108 m (Figure 8a) are about five times lower than those seen near the surface. The overall magnitudes of convergence/divergence are significantly lower in latitudes outside the ITCZ at 4108 m. However, at 1515 m, for latitudes outside the ITCZ, convergence/divergence are considerably stronger. In fact, at 1515 m, to the north of the Equator, the pattern of convergence

FIGURE 8 Composites of convergence (left) and relative vertical vorticity (right) at 1515 m (bottom) and 4108 m (top). See Figure 3 for details regarding the shading and abscissa labels. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.com)]

followed by divergence is reversed with respect to the surface, further supporting the presence of a shallow circulation. For latitudes 5° north of the Atlantic ITCZ, convergence is seen, consistent with higher values of η in the Atlantic basin (Figure 7d). The presence of divergence in latitudes south of the Equator prevents the development of strong clockwise turning flow in the Atlantic basin at 1515 m (Figure 8d), compared with the surface. On the other hand, in the East Pacific, the presence of weaker divergence south of the Equator enables the development of stronger clockwise turning flow at 1515 m, compared with the surface. The magnitude of relative vorticity at 1515 m is higher in the East Pacific ITCZ compared with the Atlantic ITCZ, as expected from its more northward position. However, at 4108 m (Figure 8b), ζ in the Atlantic ITCZ is slightly higher in magnitude than that in the East Pacific ITCZ.

The vertical structure (from the surface up to 4.5 km) of zonal- and seasonal-mean convergence superimposed with the seasonal- and zonal-mean meridional circulation for the year 2020 in both basins is shown in Figure 9. The latitudes of neutral inertial stability ($\eta = 0$) and westerly wind onset ($U = 0$) are depicted by solid and dashed lines, respectively. In both basins, the regions of divergence and convergence make a V-shaped pattern centered at the Equator in the latitude–height plane. These V-shaped structures manifest as alternating patterns of divergence and convergence in the composites at 1515 m (Figure 8c) and 4108 m (Figure 8a). The convergence associated with the ITCZ—seen until a height of 1.5 km—is seen to be characterized by westerly zonal wind in both

basins. Dominant values of convergence are seen in the southerly wind regions about 3° south of the confluence in both basins—indicating asymmetry as suggested by the observations (Hastenrath & Lamb, 1977; Windmiller & Stevens, 2024)—starting from the surface and continuing to heights up to 1 km.

The height at which the near-surface divergence changes to convergence exhibits a latitudinal dependence. At the Equator, this height is approximately 1 km and increases as one moves away from it, in both hemispheres. The return flow to the south of the ITCZ is seen at heights as low as 1.5 km (consistent with the findings of Zhang *et al.*, 2004) in the East Pacific basin, and slightly deeper around 3 km in the Atlantic basin. To the north of the ITCZ, however, the return flow is much deeper in both basins (around 4 km in Atlantic and possibly deeper in the East Pacific). This is consistent with what we observed in the composites of convergence at 1515 m (Figure 8c) and 4108 m (Figure 8a). The location of neutral inertial instability, $\eta = 0$, is equatorward of the convergence in both basins, consistent with the composites of η at 311 m (Figure 4a), 1515 m (Figure 7d), and 4108 m (Figure 7b).

5 | DISCUSSION

The dynamical structure of the lower atmosphere over the East Pacific and Atlantic basins, when SST is maximized north of the Equator, is asymmetrical and exhibits many similarities, which are summarized in

FIGURE 9 Vertical structure of seasonal- and zonal-mean convergence in (a) East Pacific and (b) Atlantic basins for JJA 2020. The solid lines indicate the location of neutral inertial instability, $\eta = 0$, and the dashed lines denote the onset of westerlies, $U = 0$. The quivers are shown to indicate the seasonal- and zonal-mean meridional overturning circulation, where the vertical wind is scaled by a factor of 100. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 10

A conceptual figure based on the dynamics seen in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins when SST is maximized poleward of the Equator. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Figure 10. Consistent with the hypothesis of Tomas and Webster (1997), we find that (i) both basins are characterized by a broad region of inertial instability (parcel criterion) north of the Equator, which extends up to height

levels of 1515 m, and (ii) regions of inertial instability are preceded by regions of divergence south of the Equator. However, our composites reveal that the convergent regions are located at least a few degrees poleward of $\eta =$

TABLE 1 A summary of dominant processes leading to the observed asymmetry, for heights near the surface.

Quantity	Between Equator and $\lambda_{PW, max}$	In the vicinity of $\lambda_{PW, max}$	To the north of $\lambda_{PW, max}$
Zonal wind	Easterly	Westerly	Easterly
Meridional wind	Southerly	Southerly (dominant)	Northerly
Convergence (C)	Divergent	Highly convergent	Weak convergence followed by divergence
Vorticity (ζ)	Negative	Highly positive	Positive
Meridional momentum	Pressure gradients + Coriolis \leftrightarrow advection + friction	Pressure gradients + advection \leftrightarrow Coriolis + friction	Pressure gradients \leftrightarrow Coriolis + friction

FIGURE 11 The dependence of monthly mean relative vorticity in the ITCZ at (a) 311 m, (b) 1515 m, and (c) 4108 m at the monthly mean ITCZ latitude (PW maximum). The Pearson correlation coefficients between monthly mean values of ζ_{ITCZ} and ITCZ latitude (PW maximum) at 311, 1515, and 4108 m are 0.505, 0.841, and 0.242, respectively. [Colour figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/terms-and-conditions)]

0 and well within an inertially stable region, disagreeing with the hypothesis of Tomas and Webster (1997). The dynamics can be easily understood by mean momentum balance: equatorial pressure gradients close to the surface can only be balanced by advection, implying southerlies accelerating and leading to divergence. These equatorial pressure gradients are absent aloft (a consequence of the weak temperature gradient approximation) and, as a result, the acceleration of the southerly flow would take the form of a wall-bounded jet. As the southerlies move poleward of the Equator and strengthen, their relative vorticity decreases due to the advection of absolute vorticity, and the tendency of the wind to turn westerly increases. The meridional flow decelerates when the winds turn westerly, as Coriolis and friction balance the pressure gradients and advection. This dynamic nature of convergence

of southerly winds is fundamentally different from that seen in the northerly flow, where pressure gradients can be easily balanced by easterlies, owing to their more poleward location. While the dynamic acceleration and deceleration of southerly flow concentrates convergence in the southerlies, a weak frictional convergence is seen over a broad meridional extent in the northerly flow (Figure 9). Pressure gradients can be maintained over a deeper layer to the north of the ITCZ, owing to their more poleward location; the strength of easterlies increases in these latitudes at higher levels. These findings are summarized in Table 1.

As the latitude of SST maximum in the East Pacific is located more poleward compared with the Atlantic, interesting differences also exist between the dynamics of the two basins. The dip in pressure in the ITCZ is much

more pronounced in the East Pacific, as it is easier to balance the pressure gradients due to convective warming with easterly winds in more poleward locations. Another interesting difference between the two basins is the presence of stronger cyclonic absolute and relative vorticities (except at 4108 m) in the East Pacific ITCZ. The amplification of vorticity in the ITCZ, due to the process of vortex stretching given by ηC , depends on the latitude of the ITCZ through $\eta \equiv \zeta + f$. Figure 11 plots the monthly mean relative vorticity in the ITCZ (ζ_{ITCZ}) extracted from the composites, as a function of the monthly mean ITCZ latitude in both East Pacific and Atlantic basins. On average, the monthly mean vorticity in both the East Pacific and Atlantic ITCZ at all three height levels increases with the latitude of the ITCZ. The correlation coefficients at 311, 1515, and 4108 m, when both East Pacific and Atlantic basins are considered together, are 0.505, 0.841, and 0.242, respectively. At 4108 m (Figure 11c), the points are clustered based on the basin considered and, for a given latitude, the Atlantic ITCZ has higher relative vorticity. This could be a result of slightly higher magnitudes of convergence in the Atlantic ITCZ, or other key processes in the vorticity equation, such as the tilting we neglected in Section 2.3, or due to the presence of African easterly jet.

6 | CONCLUSIONS

The dynamical structure of the lower atmosphere in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins during boreal summer is analyzed, as it represents the case in which sea-surface temperatures are maximized poleward of the Equator. Simulation data from a global storm-resolving Sapphire version of the ICON model are utilized in this study. Observations in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins during boreal summer depict a complex and asymmetrical lower atmospheric structure. Convection in the ITCZ is seen to span a broad meridional extent, and is often edge-intensified, with a higher amount of precipitation at the southern edge compared with the northern edge.

Our analysis shows that the mean momentum balance can explain the observed asymmetrical structure. We find the following.

1. *Close to the surface.* A minimum in SST south of the Equator is seen to increase the surface pressure at near-equatorial latitudes, leading to stronger cross-equatorial pressure gradients. These increasingly negative pressure gradients north of the Equator cannot be balanced by zonal winds alone (negligible Coriolis parameter). This necessitates the presence of non-zero

meridional velocity advection in near-equatorial latitudes, and drives the acceleration of southerlies north of the Equator. This cross-equatorial southerly flow advects negative absolute vertical vorticity into the Northern Hemisphere, and leads to the development of negative relative vorticity and clockwise turning tendencies. As the southerlies move poleward, the negative relative vorticity in the flow turns the zonal winds westerly. The intensifying westerlies, together with surface friction, can balance the negative pressure gradients and advection, leading to the deceleration of the southerlies and dynamic convergence. On the other hand, as the northerlies exist in more poleward latitudes, pressure gradients can be balanced more easily by easterly winds and friction throughout their approach to the confluence region. The mechanism of dynamical acceleration and deceleration of meridional winds that is present in the southerly regime is absent in the northerly regime, contributing to the asymmetry.

2. *Aloft.* Due to the weak temperature gradient approximation, pressure gradients are negligible in near-equatorial latitudes. North of the Equator, at 1515 m, the southerly flow is seen to be converging. The divergence at the surface, together with convergence aloft, drives a shallow circulation to the south of the ITCZ, with return flow at 2 and 4 km in the East Pacific and Atlantic basins. Inertial instability and a westerly wind region are seen at 1515 m and are absent at 4108 m. To the north of the ITCZ, pressure gradients are seen to increase with height, and, as a consequence, the strongest easterlies are located at 4108 m to the north of the ITCZ.

Overall, we notice that the dynamics of the southerly flow, which occupies more near-equatorial latitudes, is fundamentally different compared with that of the northerly flow, located more poleward. While inertial instability in the southerly flow contributes to the asymmetry, it does not decide the latitude of convection as previously hypothesized. The dynamical convergence mechanism concentrates the convection in the southerly regime. We also observe that vorticity in the ITCZ is strongly dependent on the meridional location of the ITCZ, and is seen to increase as the ITCZ moves north.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Some of the simulation data are available via the intake catalog: <https://data.nextgems-h2020.eu/online.yaml>. Access to additional data, currently stored on DKRZ cluster Levante, can be made available upon request. The codes used for analysis can be found at <https://github.com/dspraturi/BorealSummerITCZDynamics.git>.

ORCID

Divya Sri Praturı <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2889-7433>

Bjorn Stevens <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3795-0475>

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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